

MEANINGFUL NATURES IN NORDHAVN

BASELINE REPORT

*Exploring Perceptions of Meaningful
Natures in Nordhavn*

*„There are two sides of wild nature.
The beauty in uncontrolled situations and the danger it
poses to different groups.“*

- Photovoice Participant

AUTHORS

Natalie Marie Gulsrud and Csilla Duray have led this project in collaboration with Sofie Burgos-Thorsen, Natalia Rodríguez Castañeda, Andrea Šupová, Theresa Trüper, and Megan Lynn Maurer. The Living Lab is managed by Michele Merrill Betsill, Natalie Marie Gulsrud, Mark Vacher, Csilla Duray, and Mette Frimodt-Møller.

Report Authors:

Csilla Duray, Natalie Marie Gulsrud, Natalia Rodríguez Castañeda, Andrea Šupová, Theresa Trüper, Megan Lynn Maurer, Sofie Burgos-Thorsen

Author contributions:

Data Collection Lead:

Sofie Burgos-Thorsen (Photovoice), Megan Lynn Maurer (PPGIS), Natalie Marie Gulsrud (Photovoice, PPGIS)

Data Analysis Lead:

Csilla Duray, Sofie Burgos-Thorsen, Andrea Šupová, Theresa Trüper

Graphics:

Theresa Trüper, Andrea Šupová, Csilla Duray, Sofie Burgos-Thorsen

Support Team:

Megan Lynn Maurer, Anton Stahl Olafsson, Oriol García Antúnez

UNIVERSITY OF
COPENHAGEN

UNIVERSITY OF COPENHAGEN
GREEN SOLUTIONS CENTRE

PREFACE

This report is based on the pilot project “Planning for People, Place, and Planet”, part of the Living Lab Urban Solutions to the Green Transition, supported by the Green Solutions Centre (GSC) at the University of Copenhagen. The project, which ran between January 2024 to April 2025, bridges academic research with actionable tools for building more just and sustainable urban environments.

The findings presented in this report are based on preliminary analysis of raw data and represent the initial outcomes of the pilot project. Further research is required to conduct a comprehensive investigation of the dataset. We welcome inquiries from potential partners and collaborators interested in supporting the next phase of analysis. This report is intended for urban planners, policymakers, residents of Copenhagen and Nordhavn, researchers, and all those committed to making Copenhagen a greener and more inclusive city.

We extend our thanks to the residents of Østerbro and Nordhavn and the students and professionals who participated in this project.

This report has been reviewed by Anton Stahl Olafsson and Megan Lynn Maurer.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Authors	3
Preface	5
Key terms	8
Executive Summary and Key Recommendations	10
1. Introduction	12
2. Nordhavn	18
3. Methodological Overview	20
4. What makes nature meaningful? - <i>Our Findings</i>	22
4.1 Nature has many meanings	24
4.2 Overarching wish for “wild”	26
4.3 Ambivalence of “messy” nature	28
4.4 Access to water is in demand	30
4.5 Biodiverse nature is preferred	32
4.6 Nature provides a space to meet	34
5. What does this mean for planning for dense, green, biodiverse neighbourhoods?	38
5.1 Meaningful nature can be messy nature	39
5.2 Perceived biodiversity	39
5.3 Social connections and accessibility	40
5.4 Final reflections and key recommendations	41
6. Conclusion	45
Appendix A: Who we involved and how we we collected the data	46
A.1 Mapping Resident Perspectives: The PPGIS Survey	48
A.2 Qualifying Mapped Preferences: Using Participatory Photovoice	50
A.3 Layering our data	54
7. Literature and references	56

KEY TERMS

Meaningful Nature

is a concept we adapted from “**meaningful places**”, defined as “*geographic locations to which both immediately perceived and socially constructed meanings are ascribed, and evaluative attachments are tied*”¹ to explore human-nature relationships in Nordhavn. This approach acknowledges that certain locations and types of urban nature and biodiversity carry both immediately perceived and socially constructed meanings, including aesthetic values. Additionally, we recognise that urban nature can be imbued with perceived meanings, emotional connections, and personal preferences, reflecting the diverse ways people relate to natural environments in this urban district.

1 Knaps et al., 2022, p.1

Multispecies Perspective

The multispecies perspective emphasizes the interconnectedness and co-existence of humans and non-human species in urban environments. It encourages urban planners to consider not only the needs of people but also those of non-human agents such as plants, animals, and other life forms, acknowledging their shared presence and participation in the life of the city. (e.g., Houston et al., 2018; Patter et al., 2023). To learn about Nordhavn from this aspect, our pilot project works with observed and perceived biodiversity data as a way to integrate other living beings that co-exist and inhabit in the Nordhavn area. Through this research we reflected on the importance of

expanding and adapting existing methods to explore ways of integrating human and non-human agencies in urban planning.

One Health

One Health is an interdisciplinary and collaborative framework that examines health at the intersection of human, animal, and environmental well-being.² Initially proposed by veterinary and medical sciences to study zoonotic diseases—infectious diseases transmitted from animals to humans³—, the framework has recently been adapted to explore the health value of urban green spaces.⁴ This adaptation considers how interactions with urban biodiversity and green spaces benefit human health while supporting biodiversity conservation.⁵ By integrating these dimensions, One Health offers a holistic perspective on the role and planning of green spaces in fostering the health of people, ecosystems, and the broader urban environment.

2 WHO (2025)

3 Horefti (2023)

4 Rodríguez Castañeda et al. (2024); Felappi et al. (2020)

5 Rodríguez Castañeda et al. (2024)

Perceived Biodiversity

Perceived biodiversity refers to an individual's subjective assessment of species richness in an environment, particularly in urban settings⁶. Studies suggest that when people perceive greater biodiversity—such as flowers, birds, and trees—in urban spaces, their well-being is positively influenced.⁷

6 Marselle et al. (2016)

7 Dallimer et al. (2012)

PPGIS

PPGIS (Public Participation GeoInformation Systems) involves citizens and stakeholders in decision-making processes for spatial planning by asking them to map and annotate points, often through a digital mapping platform⁸. It can assist various objectives, including the identification of individual opinions and preferences for specific areas, while additionally collecting demographic data and general perspectives. This format of data collection has been successfully used by municipalities, architecture firms and researchers to learn about the perspectives of citizens as part of urban design.⁹

8 Kyttä et al. (2023)

9 Fagerholm et al. (2021); Kahila-Tani et al. (2019)

Photovoice

Photovoice is a community-based participatory research method that engages participants in identifying, representing, and enhancing their community through photographic and narrative techniques.¹⁰ This approach involves observing the environment, capturing photographs, and narrating their views and perceptions.¹¹ The primary aim of this method is to empower communities by enabling them to share their beliefs, narratives, challenges, opportunities, and perceptions of their environment.

10 Nykiforuk et al. (2011)

11 Ronzi et al. (2016)

Executive Summary

As Copenhagen advances its role as a global leader in sustainable urban development, it must carefully navigate the tensions between urban densification, climate adaptation, and biodiversity conservation. Nordhavn—a flagship site of green, dense, and transit-oriented development—offers a unique opportunity to test innovative planning approaches that integrate these priorities.

This report introduces and applies the concept of meaningful nature—urban nature that is not only ecologically functional but also accessible, socially relevant, and emotionally resonant for residents—to Copenhagen residents’ perceptions, experiences, and desires for urban nature. Drawing on participatory mapping, photo documentation, and biodiversity data, the study reveals that residents highly value wild, biodiverse spaces—even when they are harder to access—and perceive such places as more restorative, vibrant, and engaging.

These perceptions matter. Perceived biodiversity—the sensory and emotional experience of diversity in nature— shapes how people use and relate to urban green spaces. When integrated into planning, these insights can support nature-based solutions that are not only effective, but also embraced by the communities they serve.

To deliver on Copenhagen’s ambitions for climate resilience and social sustainability, planners and policymakers have an opportunity to adopt approaches that value both ecological systems and lived experiences. Meaningful nature can be planned for—through multi-scalar data, inclusive methods, and cross-species thinking—to ensure that urban environments are not only sustainable but also livable and loved.

Key Recommendations For Planners And Policy Makers

1. **Design for Meaningful Nature:** Recognize that meaningful nature is shaped not only by ecological metrics but by how people see, feel, and access it. Prioritize the design of wild and diverse natural spaces that are both visually rich and physically accessible, including small green pockets and edge habitats within dense developments.

2. **Embed One Health Thinking into Planning Practices:** Use the One Health framework to guide planning that integrates human well-being, biodiversity conservation, and urban infrastructure. Green and blue spaces should be designed as health-supporting assets for both people and non-human species.

3. **Institutionalize Participatory and Multispecies Planning Tools:** Update planning tools to include both resident perceptions and biodiversity data. Use participatory mapping, photography, and AI-assisted co-visioning to generate design insights that reflect how people and other species co-inhabit urban space.

Action Steps:

- **Incorporate** measures such as **perceived biodiversity** into green space evaluations by including public input on vegetation variety, visual interest, and natural aesthetics.
- **Ensure green spaces**—especially wild or “messy” ones—are **easy to reach** via pedestrian paths, bike lanes, and transit connections.

Action Steps:

- **Apply One Health principles** in environmental impact assessments and planning policies.
- **Promote vegetation diversity, habitat continuity** in park and streetscape design.

Action Steps:

- **Incorporate co-visioning workshops** and **participatory tools** into local consultation and neighborhood planning processes.
- **Combine citizen-generated data with scientific biodiversity indicators** to inform zoning, land use, and habitat protection.

Conclusion

Urban nature is not just a backdrop—it is a critical component of social infrastructure, biodiversity resilience, and climate adaptation. Planning for meaningful nature means

embracing both the ecological realities and the lived experiences of urban residents. By making nature more biodiverse, accessible, and emotionally engaging, planners can build cities

that are not only functional, but flourishing for people and planet alike.

1. INTRODUCTION

This report explores what constitutes meaningful nature—and for whom—in the context of a rapidly developing neighborhood in Copenhagen. Its goal is to shed light on the critical, multifunctional role urban nature plays in development processes, especially as cities face complex trade-offs between densification, climate adaptation, and biodiversity conservation. While expert assessments often emphasize the value of urban nature for climate resilience and ecological and human health, there is limited understanding of what local residents in Copenhagen consider to be “good nature,” and where they wish to see and experience it.

To meet Copenhagen’s ambitions for climate resilience and social sustainability, urban planners and policymakers have an opportunity to embrace approaches that value both ecological integrity and lived experience.

Meaningful nature can be actively planned—using multi-scalar data, inclusive methods, and cross-species perspectives—to create urban environments that are not only sustainable, but also livable and cherished.

This type of insight is particularly relevant for aligning the ongoing and future development of Nordhavn with the values and preferences of both current and future residents and users. To address this knowledge gap, the report focuses on the experiences and perspectives of Nordhavn residents and urban development professionals.

It asks: How do these groups define meaningful nature? And how can this concept guide urban development in Nordhavn toward healthier, more sustainable spaces that strengthen the relationship between people, biodiversity, and the urban landscape?

Ultimately, the report aims to outline the diverse meanings of nature in Nordhavn—a flagship site for green, dense, and transit-oriented development—and highlight how it can serve as a testing ground for innovative planning strategies that integrate ecological, social, and experiential priorities.

With 28% of assessed plant and animal species at risk of extinction¹, land use planning and monitoring must embrace new approaches, including innovative stakeholder involvement. The climate and biodiversity crises present major sustainability challenges, demanding systemic legal, political, and governance transformations. Urban areas, while significant sources of environmental pressure, are also crucial sites for solutions. In line with this, policymakers increasingly advocate for integrated nature-based solutions to address climate adaptation and biodiversity conservation.

In Copenhagen, urban nature—including parks, gardens, blue areas, and trees—is seen as a key tool for stormwater management, biodiversity awareness, and fostering community connections across neighborhoods². It plays a vital role in enhancing human well-being, promoting social cohesion, and advancing ecological sustainability. In response to growing

calls for nature protection, the city has launched a biodiversity strategy aimed at expanding and improving green spaces while balancing the need for urban densification as a step toward climate resilience and social sustainability³.

As a leader in sustainable urban development, Copenhagen has a number of strategies that emphasize green and blue infrastructures (the Copenhagen Urban Nature Strategy 2015–2025), biodiversity corridors (the Copenhagen Biodiversity Strategy 2022–2050), and community engagement (Copenhagen Municipality Plan (2024), aligning local efforts with broader European initiatives like the EU Green Deal and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 to combat climate change and biodiversity loss. Bottom-up resident engagement regarding the current and future

development of Copenhagen is also prioritized through citizen assemblies, neighborhood renewal campaigns, and online citizen petitions for policy change. For example, residents have provided concrete policy recommendations on how to allocate space to urban nature and green meeting spots based on trade-offs such as a reduction of on-street parking⁴. Here balancing land use priorities across the biodiversity and climate nexus is in focus. Yet many questions remain regarding how to balance the competing priorities of urban density, urban greening, carbon reduction, and overall human well being

⁴ We Do Democracy (2023)

³ Københavns Kommune (2022)

“Ultimately, the report aims to outline the diverse meanings of nature in Nordhavn”

¹ Rasmussen et al. (2024)

² Københavns Kommune (2015)

supported by Copenhagen's vision to be a dense and sustainable city⁵.

The Copenhagen model of development is based on selling off and developing publicly-owned brown and green fields for mixed residential and commercial use to co-finance the expansion of the Copenhagen metro line and secure a financially and socially sustainable approach to urban development⁶. This model of development has been the catalyst for Copenhagen's exceptional transition over the last 35 years from an economically failing post-industrial city to a flourishing green capital.

The Copenhagen model of transit-oriented development has been heralded as a best practice approach for green growth and urban sustainability and Nordhavn, an up-and-coming neighbourhood in Copenhagen, is often cited as a lighthouse example of this model. Nordhavn currently houses 4,500 residents but over the next 40 years is planned to house over 40,000 residents, host 35,000 jobs, and will be home to Copenhagen's newest large green space, a 28 hectare nature park that is envisioned to be a recreational space at the edge of the city⁷. The land sales for new housing and commercial development will co-finance the expansion of the city's metro line and support transit-oriented development along a 15-minute city model. By building dense and green, transit-oriented

neighbourhoods, Copenhagen is poised as a national and global leader in urban solutions to the green transition.

Yet the Copenhagen approach to sustainable urban development is challenged by the paradox that urban densification decreases space for urban nature and reduces the connectivity of urban green infrastructure, thereby decreasing the opportunity to support biodiverse and flourishing ecosystems. Specifically, there is an increasing tension between residents' support for biodiversity and nature conservation in the city and a continuously growing demand for high quality housing, dense urban development, and recreational facilities (such as turfgrass soccer fields). Each of these positions represents a stakeholder vision for the role of nature in the city. Here little is known about Copenhageners' overall preferences, values, and future visions for urban nature. Which green spaces already hold meaning for them? Where do they want more? How do they perceive biodiversity? Answering these questions provides valuable insights for decision-makers navigating the complex trade-offs associated with urban land use, particularly in rapidly developing neighborhoods.

5 Københavns Kommune (2024)

6 Katz, B. and Noring, L. (2017)

7 By&Havn, Cobe, Sleth, & RAW Mobility. (2023)

This report accordingly responds to the following questions:

How can the concept of meaningful nature shape future urban development in Nordhavn to foster healthier, more sustainable spaces that strengthen connections between people, biodiversity, and the urban environment?

How do residents and industry experts define "meaningful nature"?

Key Actors of Meaningful Nature

In order to create future development projects corresponding to the environmental and social pressure, we need to consider three main actors: human, nature and the existing urban qualities on the same level and incorporate their wishes and requirements equally into the future environments.

Figure 04: Triangle of the three main actors: humans, nature and urban environment

2. NORDHAVN

Figure 05: Graph of Nordhavns historical development and demographics.

Source: Cobe, 2024; Šupová, Trüper, 2024. Redesigned by Authors, 2025.

Urban population growth causes densification of new neighbourhoods

Four kilometres from the centre of Copenhagen, a new city district is being developed at the old harbour of Nordhavn. It intends to house 40,000 residents and 40,000 new workers by 2050.

This development is trying to respond to an urge to accommodate a significant portion of people (over 25,000) moving to Copenhagen every year.⁴

Nordhavn is predicted to grow from ca. 6.000 inhabitants in 2023 to 40.000 by 2050

As one of Copenhagen's most ambitious transformation projects, Nordhavn offers a real-world context through which to explore how nature can be integrated into dense, fast-growing urban environments. Understanding what constitutes meaningful nature here is crucial for capturing current resident values and informing future planning decisions that aim to balance ecological resilience with social and recreational needs.

Located in the northernmost part of the city, Nordhavn is being developed on a former industrial shipyard that expanded through infill processes during the 19th and 20th centuries. Its formal transformation began in 2005 in response to Copenhagen's growing population. Today, Nordhavn is envisioned as the city's "Sustainable City of the Future"—a dense, transit-oriented neighborhood that integrates green and blue infrastructure throughout its design. This reflects Copenhagen's broader tradition of people-centered urban planning¹ and its recent efforts to promote biodiversity within the urban fabric.²

At the local level, Nordhavn exemplifies the real-world application of strategic multi-functional planning. Its new structural plan aims to balance urban density with integrated green and blue spaces³. Key initiatives include diverse recreational areas, pocket parks,

and a green loop for cyclists. Biodiversity is a core focus, with soft green borders and interconnected corridors enhancing ecological resilience. Green wedges, park avenues, and urban forests serve as multifunctional spaces for both recreation and wildlife. The plan prioritizes vibrant ecosystems, native species conservation, and accessibility, fostering a city where people and nature thrive together.

In a planning framework where urban density is equated with sustainability, however, realising these ecological priorities presents a significant challenge. Development in Nordhavn will face complex trade-offs between dense residential and commercial construction and the implementation of accessible, interconnected, and biodiverse green spaces. To address these complexities, we explore how the concept of meaningful nature can guide future development in Nordhavn. These findings also offer insights to future projects, from Naturpark Nordhavn to the artificial island of Lynetteholmen, contributing to Copenhagen's goals of resilience and ecological sustainability. By examining how nature contributes to healthy, sustainable spaces and strengthens connections between people, biodiversity, and the urban environment, we aim to identify strategies that balance urban density with ecological and social well-being.

1 Gehl, J. (2010)
2 Københavns Kommune (2022); Københavns Kommune (2024)
3 By&Havn, Cobe, Sleth, & RAW Mobility. (2023);
4 Statistics Denmark (2024); By og Havn (2009)

3. METHDODOLOGICAL OVERVIEW

This report draws on two distinct datasets to explore what makes nature meaningful in Nordhavn. Together, they offer layered insights into how users and residents perceive, experience, and value urban nature.

The first data set is a public participatory GIS data set collected by researchers from the University of Copenhagen to support data-driven planning for urban nature. **It maps residents' perceptions, preferences, and desires** related to green and blue spaces in Østerbro and Nordhavn, two northeast Copenhagen districts. The survey, inspired by citizen panels from Autumn 2021, was conducted in connection with the planning of Naturpark Nordhavn.

The second dataset provides views of planning and design professionals and consists of 1,388 annotated and geocoded photographs taken in Nordhavn by students and urban planning/design experts. This data set was collected as part of a pilot project from March to June 2024 and differentiates from the PPGIS data set as it provides a more expert-based perspective on meaningful nature in Nordhavn. It is also a visual data set that qualifies the "hotspots" of meaningful nature identified in the PPGIS data

1. PPGIS

Figure 06: Hotspot maps created from PPGIS data showing liked and disliked spaces in Nordhavn.

set. The report explores this data set to test how visual documentation can provide deeper insights into perceptions of urban nature. Further information on both methods is located in the appendix of this report.

2. PHOTOVOICE

Figure 07: The welcome screen of the photovoice app and a photo taken during the photovoice survey.

INVOLVING THE PUBLIC

Researching Meaningful Nature In Numbers

Number of participants across both studies:

3,021 participants

Number of captures pictures in Photovoice study:

1,388 eye-level photos

Number of mapped points in PPGIS study:

20,158 text-annotated geopoints

An aerial photograph of an industrial and residential area in Nordhavn, Copenhagen. The image shows a large, dark, irregularly shaped body of water in the center, surrounded by green grass and some trees. To the left and top-left, there are large areas of excavated earth and sand, with some construction equipment visible. To the right and top-right, there are industrial buildings, parking lots filled with trucks and cars, and a road. The overall scene depicts a mix of natural and man-made elements.

4. WHAT MAKES NATURE MEANINGFUL?

– Our Findings

MEANINGFUL WILD NATURE

MESSY NATURE

IMPORTANCE OF WATER

SOCIAL GREEN AREAS

Figure 09: Hotspot Map of PPGIS data showing places with high and low appeal

Fig. 11: Photo annotated with high appeal. Source: Photovoice participant, 2024.

Fig. 10: Ambiguous photos annotated with low and high appeal in Århuskvarteret. Source: Photovoice participant, 2024.

Heat Map Legend

-
High appeal (PPGIS data)
N= 12,093 spots marked with high appeal
-
Low appeal (PPGIS data)
N=1,212 spots marked with low appeal

4.1. NATURE HAS MANY MEANINGS

There is a strong and widespread desire for natural areas throughout Nordhavn, though residents interpret „nature“ in diverse ways.

Analysis of mapped data and written responses reveals a clear convergence of interests across different types of natural environments, with a shared preference for multifunctional spaces. These insights highlight the need to design urban landscapes that balance ecological preservation with opportunities for recreation and social connection—essential components in shaping Nordhavn’s sustainable future.

In the PPGIS survey, textual annotations connected to green areas labelled as “important” suggest that, besides being pleasant to be in, these sites provide space for specific activities (walking, running, bathing) and are assigned restorative qualities such as “fresh air”. On the other hand, “disliked” urban nature evokes negative qualities (“boring”, “sad”, “unsafe”) and is often characterised

by “traffic” and “construction”, reflecting the constant change of Nordhavn in development, as well as the noise related to it. Demographic analysis shows limited variation in how different groups perceive Nordhavn’s natural spaces. There is, however, a significant difference between older residents (60 years plus) who tend to emphasize the importance of ecological qualities as opposed to all other age groups that do not. Additionally, women are more likely to highlight the role of nature in supporting social interaction as opposed to men.

This pattern regarding differences between liked and disliked spaces is repeated in the Photovoice results. Photographs deemed appealing often captured scenes of “pretty,” “abundant,” or “wild” nature, described as peaceful, accessible, welcoming, and safe. In contrast, less appealing photos depicted areas perceived as stressful, excluding, inaccessible, or unsafe.

4.2. OVERARCHING WISH FOR WILD NATURE

A central challenge in the development of Nordhavn is the long-term planning horizon for the neighborhood stretching over 40 years. Here it is difficult to integrate resident perspectives when the preferences of future residents are largely unknown.¹ Current data reflects the results from residents of Nordhavn and neighboring Østerbro from 2022 - 2023 and provides a baseline of wishes for the future development for planners and decision makers to build upon. **The results of this analysis are based on 5,343 mapped points identifying preferred locations and types for future urban nature in Nordhavn.**

When asked about their wishes for the future in Nordhavn, respondents were given the opportunity to map out wishes based on different priorities such as wild nature, lawns and flowers, social areas, and sports facilities. While respondents mapped out a diversity of wishes for future facilities in Nordhavn, the desire for “wild nature” stands out and the quality that was mapped most frequently. The prompt for wild nature resulted in more mapped points than any other prompt (e.g., sports facilities--see final section for full list). Wild nature means many things to participants

but they often used terms such as biodiversity, forest, shrubs, plants, and animals. The number of mapped points for wild nature could signal a strong preference for landscapes that feel “preferably as untouched as possible,” signaling a longing for more authentic, less manicured natural environments within the urban context.

Yet, respondents also mapped wishes for diverse facilities demonstrating an interest in multi-functional landscapes. Many residents expressed a desire for well-maintained lawns and flower-filled areas, noting the current lack of greenery in Nordhavn—described by some as “almost pure concrete.” They envision more inviting, green spaces where people can gather with friends and family, enjoy picnics, and relax with views of the sea, with privacy provided by flowerbeds and bushes. These spaces are also imagined as versatile areas for activities like sports, sunbathing, and dog walking. Residents referenced places like Frederiksberg Have, Kongens Have, Østre Anlæg, and Rosenhaven in Hellerup as inspiring examples of what they hope to see in Nordhavn.

Fig. 12: Photo from photovoice survey. Source: Photovoice participant, 2024.

Figure 13: Graph showing the amount of different wishes annotated in the PPGIS survey

4.3. AMBIVALENCE

OF MESSY NATURE

Figure 14: Hotspots of where participants annotated their images with the words „messy“ and „ordered“ in the photovoice app.

Legend

- Hotspots of points annotated as „ordered“
N=101 points (Photovoice data)
- Hotspots of points annotated as „messy“
N=111 points (Photovoice data)

Analyzing ‚messy‘ nature reveals how people perceive and connect with urban biodiversity.¹ During walks in Nordhavn, participants documented where they encountered it and if they liked or disliked it.

Respondents identified “messy” nature as a key element of meaningful natural spaces, though their reactions to it were ambiguous. Among the annotated photographs labeled as “messy,” 95 were rated as highly appealing, while 67 received the lowest appeal ratings. This polarization could reveal a fundamental tension in subjective urban nature preferences: while some participants appreciate the unmanicured, wild qualities of messy nature, others associate it with neglect and disorder. As participants noted, “Messy is mostly a good thing, contradicting the controlled city,” while also distinguishing between “good” messy—natural, lively, and wild—and “bad” messy, marked by pollution and decay. This insight opens up for more questions regarding which kinds of messy natures are perceived as good or bad and why. **Could certain species be perceived as positive or negative in diverse configurations? Are results significantly linked to the person and**

their nature preferences? Is it a combination of both the respondent's subjective nature perceptions as well as the ecosystem structure?

These questions deserve future evaluation. In contrast to outer Nordhavn's more open landscapes, the densely built and "grey," residential areas of Århusgadekvarteret

and Orientkaj in Inner Nordhavn were more commonly associated with values such as "conventional" and "ordered," with Århusgadekvarteret frequently described as "pretty." Participants noted that "pretty" is a highly subjective term, reflecting a sense of community and shared aesthetic values. It was linked to harmony, natural beauty, and vibrant,

lively environments that contribute to a general sense of happiness—often represented through flowers and visual variation. Conversely, the absence of "pretty" signaled something artificial, barren, or overly controlled, such as rigid concrete blocks and straight lines, underscoring a collective preference for organic balance over sterile uniformity.

What do we mean with „messy“ nature? And when is it appealing or not appealing?

95 photos annotated with „messy“ and the „highest appeal“

67 photos annotated with „messy“ and the „lowest appeal“

Figures 15-20: Photos taken during the photovoice survey and annotated with the word „messy“. Source: Photovoice Participants, 2024.

Fig. 22: Photo annotated with the wish for „beach“. Source: Photovoice participant, 2024.

Fig. 23: Photo annotated with the word „water“. Source: Photovoice participant, 2024.

Figure 21: Wishes for beach and swimming areas from the PPGIS data overlaid with areas where water was often mentioned in the photovoice survey.

Legend

- Water (Photovoice data)
N= 255 points where water was mentioned
- Wishes for swimming areas
N= 144 wishes (PPGIS data)
- Wishes for beach areas
N= 125 wishes (PPGIS data)

4.4. ACCESS TO WATER IS IN DEMAND

Given Nordhavn's extensive waterfront, residents expressed a strong desire for more swimming opportunities, especially to relieve pressure on Sandkaj bathing area in Århusgadekvarteret—currently the only designated swimming area, which becomes overcrowded during summer. Keywords such as “swimming” and “beach” reveal a clear interest in expanding swimming access across all harbour basins, along with a specific wish for a large sandy beach that includes areas for a variety of sports—extending beyond the planned shores of the future nature park.

Figure 24: By&Havn's plans, where Strandholm is indicated to become a beach area, and Skudehavnen a water park. Source: By&Havn, 2023. Redesigned by Authors, 2025.

4.5. BIODIVERSE NATURE IS PREFERRED

Figure 25: Biodiversitetskort for Danmark.

Source: Danmark Miljøportal, 2024.

The species score in the biodiversity map:

Figure 26: Mapped photovoice data of high and low biodiversity appeal

Legend

- Fig. 27: Photo annotated with low appeal and low biodiversity. Source: Photovoice Participant, 2024

+ Fig. 28: Space experienced as high appeal and high biodiversity. Source: Photovoice Participant, 2024

Data from the walks reveal notable variation in how participants experience nature in Nordhavn. High perceived biodiversity was reported across all areas, with grass, trees, wind, water, and flowers most commonly identified as natural elements. This perception was especially strong in Nordhavnstippen, known for its wild and natural landscapes. Interestingly, urban sites like Århusgadekvarteret and Orientkaj also received unexpectedly high biodiversity scores, despite their predominantly grey, built-up environments.

Comparing participants' biodiversity perceptions with the Bioscore—a metric based on known occurrences and habitat indicators of red-listed species in Denmark—reveals an uneven alignment between perceived and actual ecological conditions. Participants indicated high levels of perceived biodiversity along Nordhavnstippen. The Bioscore dataset indicates higher biodiversity around Nordhavnstippen, while inner Nordhavn areas such as Århusgadekvarteret and Orientkaj score significantly lower. Despite this, participants frequently annotated photos from these urban areas with high perceived biodiversity. This discrepancy may reflect underreporting of species in these locations or an overestimation by participants, underscoring how urban

greenery and seasonal cues—like blooming flowers in late spring—can strongly influence perceptions of nature.

Taxonomic biodiversity should not be conflated with perceived biodiversity yet perceived biodiversity is frequently a measure of how restorative a place is for human wellbeing and mental health.¹ The results show that perceived biodiversity generally aligned with how pleasant participants found an area, though there were some exceptions. In the grey urban zones of Orientkaj and Århusgadekvarteret, some photos rated lowest in biodiversity were still seen as pleasant. This suggests that while perceived biodiversity can enhance an area's appeal, it is not the only factor shaping people's perceptions. Accessibility also seems to play a major role in this scoring. In line with several other notable studies, our findings point to perceived biodiversity (in comparison to taxonomic biodiversity) as a stronger predictor of restoration². The results of our study show that there is a need to further explore and develop the concept of perceived biodiversity. Here it could be relevant to further explore and tease out the links between appealing nature, perceived biodiversity, and human wellbeing and restoration.

¹ Rozario et al. (2023)
² Cameron et al., 2020; Dallimer et al., 2012; Schebella et al., 2019)

Figure 29: PPGIS - map: Natural areas support wishes for recreation

Legend

- Important social & community places
N= 163 mapped points (Photovoice data)
- Wishes for cafés
N=59 mapped points (PPGIS data)
- Wishes for playgrounds
N=53 mapped points (PPGIS data)
- Wishes for seating areas
N=14 mapped points (PPGIS data)

4.6. NATURE PROVIDES A SPACE TO MEET

2,119 mapped
wishes for
„wild nature“

925 mapped
wishes for
**„sports and other
facilities“**

571 mapped
wishes for
„social areas“

In Nordhavn, nature is valued not only as a recreational resource but also as a vital social space. Natural areas support a wide range of activities—such as swimming, running, hiking, fishing, dog walking, football, and skateboarding—while also fostering social interaction through green meeting points. Respondents in the PPGIS survey envision Nordhavn as a vibrant, multifunctional neighborhood that blends active leisure with everyday communal life. There is strong interest

in amenities like seating areas, playgrounds, and cafés that encourage spontaneous encounters and a sense of togetherness. As one participant noted: “Create opportunities for social activities where it makes sense to hop on your bike to get there.” Some called for cultural spaces, such as venues for smaller music events, while others emphasized the need to manage noise to avoid turning these spaces into “overcrowded party areas.” These social wishes cluster around several key hotspots—including the

site of the upcoming Naturpark Nordhavn, Tunnelfabrikken, the area next to UNICEF, and Århusgadekvarteret—and often overlap with other nature-related desires, underscoring the potential for conflict between different user groups but also the opportunity to plan and design for multifunctional, inclusive spaces.

Accessibility

Accessibility emerges as a central theme running through these desires. Participants understood “accessibility” as more than proximity. It encompassed inclusivity—spaces that are “welcoming and inclusive for all”—and the idea that everyone should have the right to engage with nature and communal spaces, regardless of mobility or physical ability. Accessibility was frequently linked to convenience, diversity, and human-focused design that supports everyday use. Barriers like gated areas, car dependence, or unwelcoming designs were viewed as major obstacles. While inner Nordhavn’s “grey” areas are generally seen as accessible—likely due to metro connections and ease of access by bike—green spaces further out, such as Tunnelfabrikken, Nordhavnstippen, and Fiskerihavnen, are often marked as inaccessible. This reflects not only the physical distance, often a ten-minute bike ride, but also the experience of navigating construction zones and traffic-heavy roads. The in-between oasis of Skudehavnen received mixed responses, perhaps due to its slightly closer location combined with the challenge of riding alongside ongoing development. These accessible, multifunctional spaces are often associated with other desirable social qualities—exemplified by comments like: “Leisure activities could benefit from being

grouped together—with the aim of minimising traffic from and to facilities.” Accessibility was the most frequently mentioned social keyword during eye-level walks, closely linked to attributes like safety, peacefulness, and a welcoming atmosphere. However, less frequent mentions of “belonging” and “feeling unsafe” suggest that while these spaces are broadly viewed as safe, they may still lack a stronger emotional or communal identity.

Accessibility of different areas is generally the **most important social quality**

Figure 30: Graph reflecting averages for social qualities in relation to appeal across sites in Nordhavn

The presence of people in these spaces also sparked mixed reactions. In wilder green areas like Nordhavnstippen, participants valued solitude and the opportunity to experience nature without interruption. Conversely, in

more developed areas like Århusgadekvarteret, the presence of others was often seen as contributing to a cozy, “hygge” atmosphere—though this could shift toward overcrowding during summer months. This duality highlights

the context-dependent nature of public space experiences, where social density can be both a cherished feature and a potential drawback, depending on the setting and season.

Figure 31: Social qualities in relation to appeal of different neighbourhoods in Nordhavn.

5. WHAT DOES THIS MEAN FOR PLANNING FOR DENSE, GREEN, BIODIVERSE NEIGHBOURHOODS?

5.1. Meaningful Nature – Messy Nature

Through this study, we explore the concept of meaningful nature from a perspective that examines people’s perceptions and beliefs about what nature is most liked or desired in Nordhavn. From a socio-ecological perspective, the notion of meaningful nature was associated with a wide range of nature types, ranging from highly managed and ‘conventional’ urban green spaces to more wild, ruderal and less managed types of nature¹. Our findings indicate that while messy nature is frequently valued for its biodiversity, and its contribution to a more dynamic and ecologically rich environment, its perception is still context-dependent. In some areas, such as Nordhavnstippen, messy nature is highly appreciated for fostering a sense of wilderness and promoting ecosystem resilience. However, in other spaces, it is viewed as a sign of abandonment, with visible waste and lack of care, and preferences for more intense management and traditional aesthetics prevail.

This ambiguous perception highlights the tension between the ecological value of ruderal landscapes and social expectations of order and maintenance in urban green and grey spaces. In post-industrial areas like Nordhavnstippen, wild and ‘messy’ nature is often appreciated for its biodiversity and

psychological benefits.² In contrast, in more structured areas such as Århusgadekvarteret and Orientkaj, intentionally designed and maintained greenery is often perceived as more aesthetically pleasing while still supporting people’s connection to nature. However, not all nature is welcomed: some participants found unmanaged or neglected spaces in these urban areas unattractive or even unsettling. This points to a complex relationship where the same qualities—such as wildness or lack of maintenance—can evoke both positive and negative responses, depending on context and individual expectations

These results suggest that the perception of meaningful nature is context-dependent, shaped by the interplay between ecological benefits, social preferences, and restorative values that evoke feelings of tranquility and pleasantness. These feelings arise not only from contact with “messy” nature, but also from more designed and managed forms of nature, such as wildflowers, street trees, and meadows.

The results also suggest that future focus could be placed on exploring undesired nature or bad nature to further unpack the sometimes ambiguous and complex social and ecological relationship with urban nature.

5.2. Perceived Biodiversity

This study also examines how meaningful nature is associated with both perceived and taxonomic biodiversity. Perceived biodiversity refers to an individual’s subjective assessment of species richness within an environment, particularly in urban settings.³ Research indicates that when people perceive greater biodiversity—such as a variety of flowers, birds, and trees—their psychological well-being, mood, and even cognitive functioning are positively influenced.⁴ This perception often draws on visual and acoustic cues from the landscape, meaning that elements like plant diversity, bird calls, insect activity, and natural textures play a significant role in shaping an individual’s experience of biodiversity.⁵

Taxonomic biodiversity, by contrast, refers to the measurable identity, abundance, and functional characteristics of species in a given location. It is typically assessed through ecological surveys, citizen science data, and remote sensing tools.⁶ This includes metrics such as species richness, evenness, and abundance, as well as the ecological roles of species present in the landscape.⁷ While taxonomic biodiversity offers a more objective picture of urban ecological health, it does not always align with what people perceive.

1 Kowarik et al. (2015)

2 Rodríguez-Castañeda, N. (2024)

3 Marselle et al. (2016)

4 Fisher et al. (2021); Dallimer et al. (2012); Schwartz et al. (2014)

5 Rozario et al. (2023)

6 Liang et al. (2021); Aronson et al. (2017)

7 Marselle et al. (2021); Niemelä (1999)

5.3. Social Connections & Accessibility

Studies have shown that people frequently over- or underestimate biodiversity based on aesthetic preferences, cultural associations, or familiarity with certain species.⁸

This divergence has important implications for urban design and planning. For instance, managed landscapes with high visual diversity—such as colorful flowerbeds or mixed tree plantings—may be perceived as biodiverse even if they support relatively few species ecologically.⁹ Conversely, ruderal or wilder areas with high taxonomic richness may be perceived as unkempt or low in biodiversity due to their less structured appearance.¹⁰ A deeper understanding of how perceived and actual biodiversity intersect can guide the development of urban green spaces that are not only ecologically functional but also resonate with people’s sensory and emotional experiences. This is essential for fostering public engagement with nature, enhancing well-being, and building broader support for biodiversity conservation in cities.¹¹

When exploring the value of urban nature in Nordhavn, the social aspect emerged as a key factor in our results. Activities such as walking, running, and bathing were positively associated with opportunities to connect with nature, whether in green or blue spaces. This positive association was also linked to accessibility, highlighting that meaningful nature is both accessible and social—providing spaces where diverse activities can take place, fostering social interactions, and strengthening a sense of community.¹²

Accessibility was not only about proximity but also about infrastructure—such as safe bike paths, pedestrian routes, and the integration of metro stations—which made these spaces easy to reach and navigate. Participants also emphasized that areas felt safe, clean, and inviting to stay in, which contributed to a sense of comfort and belonging. The presence of well-maintained facilities, seating, and lighting played a role in shaping perceptions of safety and usability.¹³

Interestingly, preferences were not uniform: while some valued structured, designed spaces, others expressed a strong desire for wilder, less manicured forms of nature.

This reflects ongoing debates in urban design about how to balance ecological function with aesthetic and recreational needs.¹⁴ The findings point to the importance of offering a diversity of green and blue spaces—ranging from intentionally designed parks to messier, more spontaneous landscapes—to support both ecological goals and the varied ways people connect with urban nature.¹⁵ Moving forward, monitoring of accessibility - from proximity and infrastructure to perceived sense of belonging and nature connectedness - will be critical to ensure that Nordhavn meets the needs of diverse residents and users, specifically as the neighborhood will host one of Copenhagen’s largest nature parks.

5.4. Final Reflections & Key Recommendations

As Copenhagen continues to position itself as a global leader in sustainable urban development, the city stands at a critical juncture where the competing demands of urban densification, climate adaptation, and biodiversity conservation must be carefully negotiated. This report underscores that nature in the city is not only a matter of ecological performance, but also of human experience, cultural meaning, and democratic participation. The concept of meaningful nature—shaped by both perceived and actual biodiversity, accessibility, social use, and experience—offers a valuable lens through which to understand and design future urban environments.

In Nordhavn, a flagship site for Copenhagen's green and dense development strategy, the stakes are especially high. With ambitious goals for housing, employment, green space, and mobility infrastructure, the district is a living laboratory for testing how urban development can align with the values and needs of its current and future residents. Findings from this study suggest that Copenhageners value a diversity of nature experiences, ranging from wild and ruderal landscapes to more structured, designed green spaces.

Importantly, these spaces are not just backdrops to everyday life—they are active sites of social interaction, recreation, sensory engagement, and environmental learning.

To meet its sustainability ambitions while maintaining public support, Copenhagen must continue to engage residents in meaningful dialogue about urban nature—how it is perceived, what it provides, and where it should be prioritized. This includes recognizing the tensions between the ecological value of biodiverse spaces and aesthetic or functional preferences, as well as the trade-offs between infrastructure expansion and green space preservation. If guided by inclusive, evidence-based planning that integrates both ecological science and social values, the city has the opportunity to create urban environments that are not only livable and resilient, but also deeply meaningful for the people who inhabit them.

KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

One Health

Moving forward, there is a clear opportunity to adopt a more holistic and integrated planning approach that prioritizes both human and ecological health within market-driven urban development. The One Health framework—originally developed in veterinary and medical sciences to study zoonotic diseases¹—has recently been adapted to examine the health benefits of urban green spaces². This interdisciplinary approach considers how interactions with urban biodiversity support human well-being while advancing biodiversity conservation.

By bridging human, environmental, and ecological health, One Health offers a valuable lens for planning green spaces that promote resilience across species and systems. In Nordhavn, applying a One Health perspective can help make visible the social, ecological, and health values embedded in different types of urban nature. It also provides a strategic framework for integrating urban nature into the district's ongoing development—ensuring that spaces are designed not only for infrastructure and growth, but for people and the planet alike.

Advancing Multispecies Urban Planning

As Nordhavn undergoes rapid transformation into a dense, sustainable, and transit-oriented urban district, there is a timely opportunity to adopt a multispecies planning perspective that recognizes the city as a shared habitat for both human and non-human life. Drawing from the One Health framework, which highlights the interdependence of human, environmental, and ecological health, and informed by biodiversity data and resident perceptions, we recommend the following:

1. Integrate Multispecies Thinking into Urban Design

Urban planning in Nordhavn could move beyond anthropocentric models and incorporate design principles that support the needs and flourishing of other species—such as birds, insects, and plants—who inhabit and co-create the urban ecosystem. This means prioritizing biodiversity corridors, nesting habitats, pollinator-friendly vegetation, and soil health in both public and private developments (Houston et al., 2018; Patter et al., 2023).

2. Use Taxonomic Biodiversity Data to Inform Land Use Decisions

Our study demonstrates that there is potential in integrating taxonomic biodiversity data into planning processes that could make non-human life visible in ways that complement human-centered approaches. These datasets offer actionable insights into species richness and habitat needs across Nordhavn and should guide zoning, landscaping, and construction to avoid ecological fragmentation.

3. Apply a One Health Framework to Green Infrastructure

By framing green space as a shared health infrastructure for people, animals, and ecosystems, planners can design parks, waterfronts, and streetscapes that support physical and mental well-being while strengthening urban biodiversity. This includes ensuring continuity between green and blue spaces, promoting plant diversity, and minimizing pollutants that harm shared environments.³

4. Institutionalize Multispecies Assessment Tools

The city should adapt and expand existing planning tools to assess the impact of development on both human and non-human communities. This could include ecological impact assessments that explicitly account for non-human species' movement, habitat connectivity, and seasonal needs, as well as participatory mapping that includes citizen observations of wildlife and plant life.

5. Promote Public Engagement with Urban Nature as a Shared Commons

Our findings show that when residents engage with urban nature—through walking, observing, and photographing biodiversity—they not only value it more but could also be motivated to advocate for its protection. Public programs and educational campaigns should frame nature as a shared commons, where care for biodiversity is tied to community well-being and stewardship.

Figure 32: Adapted One Health framework as presented in “exploring the restorative capacity of UGS from an adapted One Health approach, a scoping review” Source: Rodriguez-Castañeda et al, 2024. Redesign by Authors, 2025.

Figure 33: Picture of Nordhavnstippen, Nordhavn. Image: Kai Thiry, 2024

6. Conclusion

To meet Copenhagen's climate and biodiversity goals, a shift toward multispecies urbanism is essential. Nordhavn offers a unique opportunity to pilot this approach—one that values the entangled lives of humans and other species, and plans for cities that are not just sustainable for people, but livable and thriving for all life forms. As urban nature becomes increasingly central to sustainable city planning, novel methods are needed to capture and integrate the diverse, subjective, and often intangible ways people relate to nature.

APPENDIX A.

WHO WE INVOLVED

AND HOW WE COLLECTED DATA

Our Data Creation Process

This report draws on two distinct datasets to explore what makes nature meaningful in Nordhavn. Together, they offer layered insights into how users and residents perceive, experience, and value urban nature.

1. PPGIS

2. PHOTOVOICE

A.1 Mapping Resident Perspectives: PPGIS

GENDER

Figure 34: Gender demographics from the PPGIS survey

These data were collected between December 2022 and February 2023 in both Danish and English. A total of 2,907 participants completed the map-based survey, drawn from a representative sample of 12,250 residents in Østerbro and Nordhavn. Participants received the survey link via e-Boks, a widely used digital mailing platform for official communication. Their responses were collected using

AGE GROUP

Figure 35: Age groups of the PPGIS participants

Maptionnaire, a digital tool that integrates mapping tasks into surveys.¹

The data analysis is based on 13,427 mapped points of important and disliked natural areas as well as 5,343 geo-tagged wishes for urban nature qualities in Østerbro and Nordhavn.

Citizens living in Østerbro and Nordhavn, contacted via e-boks

18% are between 50-59 years old, 57% women

The PPGIS Survey

As part of the PPGIS survey, participants were prompted to map their *important* urban green space in Østerbro and Nordhavn.

When placing a point, they were asked the following questions:

1. *Why is this place important to you?*
(free text)
2. *How often have you visited this place during the past year?*
(Please indicate number of days the past year
(value between 1-365))
3. *Are any of the listed values below important for your relationship to this place?*
(please choose as many as you like)
 - *Relaxation and restoration*
 - *Natural value (e.g. wildlife or biodiversity)*
 - *Aesthetic value*
 - *Food (e.g. fishing, foraging, or gardening)*
 - *Social interaction*
 - *Personal or Spiritual identity*
 - *Community or Heritage value*
 - *Learning*
 - *Reduction of climate change risk*
 - *Wilderness*
 - *Walking the dog*
 - *Swimming*
- *Sports*
- *Boating*
- *Walking*
- *Other outdoor activities (If other, please specify)*

Following that, they were asked to map their *disliked* urban green space in Østerbro and Nordhavn. When placing a point, they were asked the following questions:

4. *Why is this place important to you?*
(free text)
5. *How often have you visited this place during the past year?*
(Please indicate number of days the past year
(value between 1-365))

In the third part of the survey, participants were prompted to *map their wishes* for the new park in Nordhavn. They could categorise their wishes as "*wild nature*", "*sports facilities*", "*lawns/flowers*", "*social areas*", "*other facilities*" or "*other*", and received the following questions to clarify:

6. *Please describe what kind of xxx you would like.*
(free text)
7. *Why is it important to you to have xxx here?*
(free text)

A.2 Qualifying Mapped Preferences: Photovoice

GENDER

Figure 36: Gender demographics of the photovoice participants

To further understand how people relate to Nordhavn’s urban nature, we invited students, designers, urban developers, and policymakers to participate in eye-level walks. The pilot project involved students from Aalborg University, the University of Copenhagen, and the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, as well as professionals from SLA, 3XN/ GXN, the University of Copenhagen, Analyse & Tal, Arup, Thing Brandt Landskab, Building Diversity, Copenhagen Municipality, and other organisations. Six walking sites were selected based on hot

AGE GROUP

Figure 37: Age groups of the photovoice participants

spot patterns of likes and dislikes for green and blue spaces observed in the PPGIS maps. Using the Urban Belonging App, a digital photovoice tool, participants captured and annotated geolocated images, documenting natural elements that stood out, rating sites, and reflecting on their environmental and social value. **The annotation questions we used to explore human-nature relationships in Nordhavn focused on the perceived appeal of the location, perceived biodiversity, nature elements (e.g. presence of trees, water bodies, and other green spaces), ecological qualities of the**

environment, social qualities of the environment and soundscape characteristics. A follow-up workshop in August 2024 invited participants to share their stories behind pictures they chose and discuss the meaning behind some of the ecological and social qualities. This adaptation of the photovoice method offered a situated, eye-level perspective on Nordhavn’s urban nature. The images captured specific places, elements, and moments in urban nature that evoked positive or negative feelings of meaning. Discussions based on the walk experiences additionally provided a deeper understanding of what makes nature meaningful in a dense urban environment.

Using Participatory Photovoice

The Photovoice Experience

During the walks, participants were prompted to:

“Capture positive and negative experiences of urban nature in Nordhavn”

Their annotations include:

1. Appeal: How do you experience the overall appeal of this place?

(Slide scale from 1 to 5 (1=“Unpleasant” to 5=Pleasant))

2. Biodiversity: How biodiverse do you perceive nature here to be?

(Slide scale from 1 to 5 (1=“Not biodiverse” to 5=Very diverse))

3. Nature Elements: What elements of nature do you notice in this place?

(Categorical options: ‘Trees’, ‘Grass’, ‘Flowers’, ‘Other vegetation’, ‘Stones/rocks’, ‘Soil’, ‘Gravel’, ‘Water’, ‘Birds’, ‘Dogs’, ‘Insects’, ‘Other non-human species’, ‘Wind’, ‘Rain’, ‘Sun’ and ‘Other’ (Your own keywords))

4. Nature Qualities: How would you describe the quality of nature here?

(Categorical options: ‘Abundant’, ‘Monotonous’, ‘Messy’, ‘Ordered’, ‘Protected’, ‘Well cared for’, ‘Unequally distributed’, ‘Politically driven’, ‘Wild’, ‘Conventional’, ‘Pretty’, ‘Ugly’ and ‘Other’ (Your own keywords))

5. Social Qualities: How do you experience the social quality of this place?

(Categorical options: ‘Accessible’, ‘Not accessible’, ‘Well-protected’, ‘Over-protected’, ‘Welcoming’, ‘Excluding’, ‘Peaceful’, ‘Stressful’, ‘Feels safe’, ‘Feels unsafe’, ‘Feeling of belonging’, ‘Feeling alienated’ and ‘Other’ (Your own keywords))

6. Soundscape: Which sounds do you notice in this place?

(Categorical options: ‘Construction’, ‘Traffic’, ‘Wind/ weather’, ‘Water’, ‘Insects’, ‘Birds’, ‘Human chatter’ and ‘Other’ (Your own keywords))

Figure 38: Interface of the Urban Belonging App.

After capturing a photo, participants were asked to annotate the photo according to six questions. Photos and walked routes were automatically geolocated within the app, after each person gave consent to allow this tracking.

Other metadata automatically collected:

Image geolocation:

Geolocation of each captured photo.

Image timestamp:

Timestamp of when each photo is captured.

Walked route:

Geolocated route walked during each photo task.

Photo walk start + end:

Timestamp for when photo walks are started and ended by participants.

The data collected through Photovoice is available online, and you are welcome to play around with it. Please cite us if you use the data.

Dashboard link:

<https://tinyurl.com/livinglabnordhavn>

Reference:

Burgos-Thorsen, S., Gulsrud, N.M., & Duray, C. (2024) "Planning for People, Place, and Planet: Nature Futures in Developing Urban Areas."

Figure 39: Dashboard for the data overview of the Urban Belonging App. Source: Burgos-Thorsen, S., Gulsrud, N.M., & Duray, C. (2024)

A.3 Layering Our Data

The two datasets described above—PPGIS survey responses and participatory photography—were collected at different perceptual and analytical levels. This multi-level approach enables a deeper understanding of urban nature by combining macro-scale spatial patterns with lived, ground-level experiences. Digitally mapped PPGIS responses offer a bird's-eye view, useful for identifying broad spatial trends and community preferences across Nordhavn. In contrast, geotagged photographs and annotations provide rich documentation of in-situ experiences, capturing how students and professionals perceive and interact with urban nature on a personal level.

Geolocated data serves as a shared spatial reference, enabling integration across datasets and allowing for spatial comparisons and contextual insights. Textual and in-person discursive data often overlap, supporting thematic and semantic analysis, while image data adds a visual dimension that can uncover

patterns not easily conveyed through text or numbers alone.

By combining these diverse data types, the project supports a range of analytical outputs—including discourse analysis (both close reading of individual accounts and distant reading across large datasets) and visual representations such as maps and overlays that integrate geospatial, textual, and visual data for intuitive interpretation and effective communication.

Overlaying datasets collected at different levels and through different methods creates a unique opportunity to generate multidimensional insights into urban nature perceptions and future visions for Nordhavn. This integration allows complex questions to be approached with nuance and sensitivity to context. Our pilot project produced a thick dataset—a layered collection of geolocations, narratives, and images—that can be explored through

multiple research lenses. Unlike big data, thick data prioritizes depth, meaning, and situated understanding, offering a strong foundation for participatory planning and knowledge co-production.¹

Layering of the data from the two distinct datasets exploring what makes nature meaningful in Nordhavn. Together, they offer layered insights into how users and residents perceive, experience, and value urban nature in the form of detailed qualitative data sets.

7. LITERATURE AND REFERENCES

FIGURES:

Fig. 2, 3, 8, 33: Thiry, K. (2024). Images [Photograph].

Fig. 1, 7, 10-12, 15-20, 22-23, 27-28: Photovoice survey participants. (2024). Images [Photographs]

Fig. 5: By&Havn, Cobe, Sleth, & RAW Mobility. (2023). Strukturplan Ydre Nordhavn. [Maps].; Šupova, A. Trüper, T. (2024). Greenhub Orientkaj - A Pilot Project for a social hub for everyone - People and Nature [Master Thesis]. Graphic - Nordhavn Development. [Graph]. Det kgl. bibliotek, <https://soeg.kb.dk/>

Fig. 7, 30-31, 38: Burgos-Thorsen, S., Gulsrud, N.M., & Duray, C. (2024) "Planning for People, Place, and Planet: Nature Futures in Developing Urban Areas.", <https://tinyurl.com/livinglabnordhavn>

Fig. 24: By&Havn, (2023). Strukturplan Ydre Nordhavn. [Plan]. Redesigned by Authors, 2025.

Fig. 25: Arealdata, Danmark Miljøportal, 2024. <https://arealdata.miljoportal.dk/>

Fig. 32: Rodriguez Castañeda, N., Pineda-Pinto, M., Gulsrud, N. M., Cooper, C., O'Donnell, M., & Collier, M. (2024). Exploring the restorative capacity of urban green spaces and their biodiversity through an adapted One Health approach: A scoping review. In *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* (Vol. 100, p. 128489). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128489> . Redesigned by Authors, 2025.

Fig. 39: Burgos-Thorsen, S., Gulsrud, N.M., & Duray, C. (2024) "Planning for People, Place, and Planet: Nature Futures in Developing Urban Areas.", <https://tinyurl.com/livinglabnordhavn>

Fig. 4, 6, 9, 14, 21, 26, 29, 34-37: Project Team: Trüper, T. Šupová, A. Duray, C. Burgos-Thorsen, S. (2024, 2025). Graphics, Maps

All other graphics in the report have been created by Šupová, A., Trüper, T. (2025)

LITERATURE:

Key Terms:

Fagerholm, N., Raymond, C. M., Olafsson, A. S., Brown, G., Rinne, T., Hasanzadeh, K., Broberg, A., & Kytä, M. (2021). A methodological framework for analysis of participatory mapping data in research, planning, and management. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 35(9), 1848–1875. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2020.1869747>

Felappi, J. F., Sommer, J. H., Falkenberg, T., Terlau, W., & Kötter, T. (2020). Green infrastructure through the lens of "One Health": A systematic review and integrative framework uncovering synergies and trade-offs between mental health and wildlife support in cities. In *Science of The Total Environment* (Vol. 748, p. 141589). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.141589>

Horetti, E. (2023). The Importance of the One Health Concept in Combating Zoonoses. In *Pathogens* (Vol. 12, Issue 8, p. 977). MDPI AG. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens12080977>

Houston, D. (2018). Planning multispecies cities. Digital or Visual products, City Road Podcast. <https://cityroadpod.org/2018/08/27/planning-multispecies-cities/>

Kahila-Tani, M., Kytä, M., & Geertman, S. (2019). Does mapping improve public participation? Exploring the pros and cons of using public participation GIS in urban planning practices. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 186, 45–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2019.02.019>

Knaps, F., S. Gottwald, C. Albert, and S. Herrmann. 2022. Using meaningful places as an indicator for sense of place in the management of social-ecological systems. *Ecology and Society* 27(4):9. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-13340-270409>

Kytä, M., Fagerholm, N., Hausner, V. H., & Broberg, A. (2023). Maptionnaire. In C. M. Burnett (Ed.), *Evaluating Participatory Mapping Software* (pp. 71–91). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19594-5_4

Nykiforuk, C. I. J., Vallianatos, H., & Nieuwendyk, L. M. (2011). Photovoice as a Method for Revealing Community Perceptions of the Built and Social Environment. In *International Journal of Qualitative Methods* (Vol. 10, Issue 2, pp. 103–124). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.1177/160940691101000201>

Marselle, M. R., Irvine, K. N., Lorenzo-Arribas, A., & Warber, S. L. (2016). Does perceived restorativeness mediate the effects of perceived biodiversity and perceived naturalness on emotional well-being

following group walks in nature? In *Journal of Environmental Psychology* (Vol. 46, pp. 217–232). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2016.04.008>

Rodriguez Castañeda, N., Pineda-Pinto, M., Gulsrud, N. M., Cooper, C., O'Donnell, M., & Collier, M. (2024). Exploring the restorative capacity of urban green spaces and their biodiversity through an adapted One Health approach: A scoping review. In *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* (Vol. 100, p. 128489). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128489>

Ronzi, S., Pope, D., Orton, L., & Bruce, N. (2016). Using photovoice methods to explore older people's perceptions of respect and social inclusion in cities: Opportunities, challenges and solutions. In *SSM - Population Health* (Vol. 2, pp. 732–745). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssmph.2016.09.004>

Van Patter, L. E. (2022). Toward a More-Than-Human Everyday Urbanism: Rhythms and Sensoria in the Multispecies City. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 113(4), 913–932. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2022.2134838>

Van Patter, L.E., Linares-Roake, J. & Breen, A.V. What does One Health want? Feminist, posthuman, and anti-colonial possibilities. *One Health Outlook* 5, 4 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42522-022-00076-9>

WHO (2025). <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/one-health>

1. Introduction:

By&Havn, Cobe, Sleth, & RAW Mobility. (2023). *Strukturplan Ydre Nordhavn*.

Katz, B. and Norring, L. (2017). THE COPENHAGEN CITY AND PORT DEVELOPMENT CORPORATION: A Model for Regenerating Cities. The Brookings Institute. https://www.brookings.edu/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/csi_20170601_copenhagen_port_paper.pdf

Kleinert, S., & Horton, R. (2016). Urban design: an important future force for health and wellbeing. In *The Lancet* (Vol. 388, Issue 10062, pp. 2848–2850). Elsevier BV. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(16\)31578-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(16)31578-1)

Københavns Kommune (2015). *Bynatur i København—Strategi for 2015-2025*. <https://www.kk.dk/politik/politikker-og-indsatser/klima-og-miljoe/bynatur-i-koebenhavn>

Københavns Kommune (2022). *Biodiversitet i København—Strategi 2022-2050*. <https://biodiversitet.kk.dk/koebenhavns-nye-strategi-for-biodiversitet>

We Do Democracy (2023). *Citizens' assembly on green urban life in Inner Østerbro*. <https://www.wedodemocracy.com/case/citizens-assembly-on-green-urban-life-in-inner-oesterbro-2/>

Københavns Kommune (2024). *Københavns Kommuneplan 2024. Fremtidens klimavenlige hovedstad*. <https://www.kk.dk/sites/default/files/2025-01/KP24%20webtilg%C3%A6ngelig.pdf>

Rasmussen, J. H., Stowell, D., & Briefer, E. F. (2024). Sound evidence for biodiversity monitoring. In *Science* (Vol. 385, Issue 6705,

pp. 138–140). American Association for the Advancement of Science (AAAS). <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adh2716>

2. Nordhavn:

By&Havn, Cobe, Sleth, & RAW Mobility. (2023). *Strukturplan Ydre Nordhavn*.

Gehl, J. (2010). *Cities for People*. Island Press.

Københavns Kommune (2022). *Biodiversitet i København—Strategi 2022-2050*. <https://biodiversitet.kk.dk/koebenhavns-nye-strategi-for-biodiversitet>

Københavns Kommune (2024). *Københavns Kommuneplan 2024. Fremtidens klimavenlige hovedstad*. <https://www.kk.dk/sites/default/files/2025-01/KP24%20webtilg%C3%A6ngelig.pdf>

4.2 Overarching wish for wild nature:

Gulsrud, N. M., Betsill, M. M., Duray, C., Vacher, M., Frimodt-Møller, M., & Lassen, D. D. (2023). *Urban Solutions to the Green Transition: Knowledge gaps and a research agenda from the Living Lab in Nordhavn, Copenhagen*. Green Solutions Centre. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10276653>

4.3 Ambivalence of messy nature:

Hoyle, H., Hitchmough, J., & Jorgensen, A. (2017). All about the 'wow factor'? The relationships between aesthetics, restorative effect and perceived biodiversity in designed urban planting. In *Landscape and Urban Planning* (Vol. 164, pp. 109–

123). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2017.03.011>

Wartmann, F. M., & Lorimer, J. (2024). Messy natures: The political aesthetics of nature recovery. In *People and Nature* (Vol. 6, Issue 6, pp. 2564–2576). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10743>

4.4 Biodiverse nature is preferred:

Dallimer, M., Irvine, K. N., Skinner, A. M. J., Davies, Z. G., Rouquette, J. R., Maltby, L. L., Warren, P. H., Armsworth, P. R., & Gaston, K. J. (2012). Biodiversity and the Feel-Good Factor: Understanding Associations between Self-Reported Human Well-being and Species Richness. In *BioScience* (Vol. 62, Issue 1, pp. 47–55). Oxford University Press (OUP). <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2012.62.1.9>

Rozario, K., Oh, R. R. Y., Marselle, M., Schröger, E., Gillerot, L., Ponette, Q., Godbold, D., Haluza, D., Kilpi, K., Müller, D., Roeber, U., Verheyen, K., Muys, B., Müller, S., Shaw, T., & Bonn, A. (2023). The more the merrier? Perceived forest biodiversity promotes short-term mental health and well-being—A multicentre study. *People and Nature*, 6(1), 180–201. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10564>

5. What does it mean for planning for dense, green, biodiverse neighbourhoods?

Dallimer, M., Irvine, K. N., Skinner, A. M. J., Davies, Z. G., Rouquette, J. R., Maltby, L. L., Warren, P. H., Armsworth, P. R., & Gaston, K. J. (2012). Biodiversity and the Feel-Good

Factor: Understanding Associations between Self-Reported Human Well-being and Species Richness. In *BioScience* (Vol. 62, Issue 1, pp. 47–55). Oxford University Press (OUP). <https://doi.org/10.1525/bio.2012.62.1.9>

European Environment Agency (2022). Who benefits from nature in cities? Social inequalities in access to urban green and blue spaces across Europe. <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/who-benefits-from-nature-in>

Fisher, J. C., Irvine, K. N., Bicknell, J. E., Hayes, W. M., Fernandes, D., Mistry, J., & Davies, Z. G. (2021). Perceived biodiversity, sound, naturalness and safety enhance the restorative quality and wellbeing benefits of green and blue space in a neotropical city. *Science of The Total Environment* (Vol. 755, p. 143095). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.143095>

Hoyle, H., Hitchmough, J., & Jorgensen, A. (2017). All about the 'wow factor'? The relationships between aesthetics, restorative effect and perceived biodiversity in designed urban planting. In *Landscape and Urban Planning* (Vol. 164, pp. 109–123). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2017.03.011>

Hoyle, H., Norton, B., Dunnett, N., Richards, J. P., Russell, J. M., & Warren, P. (2018). Plant species or flower colour diversity? Identifying the drivers of public and invertebrate response to designed annual meadows. In *Landscape and Urban Planning* (Vol. 180, pp. 103–113). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2018.08.017>

Kleinert, S., & Horton, R. (2016). Urban design: an important future force for health and wellbeing. In *The Lancet* (Vol. 388, Issue 10062, pp. 2848–2850). Elsevier BV. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(16\)31578-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(16)31578-1)

Kowarik, I. (2018). Urban wilderness: Supply, demand, and access. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 29, 336–347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2017.05.017>

Lengieza, M. L., Richardson, M., & Aviste, R. (2025). Situation networks: The emotions and activities that are central to nature-connectedness experiences. In *Journal of Environmental Psychology* (Vol. 101, p. 102491). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2024.102491>

Liang, M., Liang, C., Hautier, Y., Wilcox, K. R., & Wang, S. (2021). Grazing-induced biodiversity loss impairs grassland ecosystem stability at multiple scales. In I. Donohuev (Ed.), *Ecology Letters* (Vol. 24, Issue 10, pp. 2054–2064). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13826>

Liang, H., Lin, Y., Chen, Y., Hao, X., Gao, D., Yu, N., Li, Y., Qiu, L., & Gao, T. (2023). The relationships among biodiversity, perceived biodiversity and recreational preference in urban green spaces—A case study in Xianyang, China. In *Ecological Indicators* (Vol. 146, p. 109916). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2023.109916>

Lund, L. N. (2024). BiodiversitetsTaktik. <https://www.futurista.dk/biodiversitetstaktik-site>
Maptionnaire (2025). About Maptionnaire. <https://www.maptionnaire.com/>

Marselle, M. R., Irvine, K. N., Lorenzo-Arribas, A., & Warber, S. L. (2016). Does perceived restorativeness mediate the effects of perceived biodiversity and perceived naturalness on emotional well-being following group walks in nature? In *Journal of Environmental Psychology* (Vol. 46, pp. 217–232). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2016.04.008>

Marselle, M. R., Hartig, T., Cox, D. T. C., de Bell, S., Knapp, S., Lindley, S., Triguero-Mas, M., Böhning-Gaese, K., Braubach, M., Cook, P. A., de Vries, S., Heintz-Buschart, A., Hofmann, M., Irvine, K. N., Kabisch, N., Kolek, F., Kraemer, R., Markevych, I., Martens, D., ... Bonn, A. (2021). Pathways linking biodiversity to human health: A conceptual framework. In *Environment International* (Vol. 150, p. 106420). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106420>

Miller, A. B., Blahna, D. J., Morse, W. C., Leung, Y.-F., & Rowland, M. M. (2022). From recreation ecology to a recreation ecosystem: A framework accounting for social-ecological systems. In *Journal of Outdoor Recreation and Tourism* (Vol. 38, p. 100455). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jort.2021.100455>

Qiu, L., Lindberg, S., & Nielsen, A. B. (2013). Is biodiversity attractive?—On-site perception of recreational and biodiversity values in urban green space. In *Landscape and Urban Planning* (Vol. 119, pp. 136–146). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2013.07.007>

Rodriguez Castañeda, N. (2024). Reflections towards a multispecies ethnography perspective in Nordhavstippen, Copenhagen, Denmark. *NovelEco*. <https://noveleco.eu/>

reflections-towards-a-multispecies-ethnography-perspective-in-nordhavstippen-copenhagen-denmark/

Rozario, K., Oh, R. R. Y., Marselle, M., Schröger, E., Gillerot, L., Ponette, Q., Godbold, D., Haluza, D., Kilpi, K., Müller, D., Roeber, U., Verheyen, K., Muys, B., Müller, S., Shaw, T., & Bonn, A. (2023). The more the merrier? Perceived forest biodiversity promotes short-term mental health and well-being—A multicentre study. *People and Nature*, 6(1), 180–201. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10564>

Rugel, E. J., Carpiano, R. M., Henderson, S. B., & Brauer, M. (2019). Exposure to natural space, sense of community belonging, and adverse mental health outcomes across an urban region. In *Environmental Research* (Vol. 171, pp. 365–377). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.01.034>

Tribot, A.-S., Deter, J., & Mouquet, N. (2018). Integrating the aesthetic value of landscapes and biological diversity. In *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* (Vol. 285, Issue 1886, p. 20180971). The Royal Society. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rspb.2018.0971>

Troudet, J., Grandcolas, P., Blin, A. et al. Taxonomic bias in biodiversity data and societal preferences. *Sci Rep* 7, 9132 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-09084-6>

van den Bosch, M., & Sang, A. (2017). Urban Natural Environments As Nature Based Solutions for Improved Public Health – a Systematic Review of Reviews. In *Journal of Transport & Health* (Vol. 5, p. S79). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2017.05.230>

[org/10.1016/j.jth.2017.05.230](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2017.05.230)

Van Patter, L. E. (2022). Toward a More-Than-Human Everyday Urbanism: Rhythms and Sensoria in the Multispecies City. *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 113(4), 913–932. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2022.2134838>

Van Patter, L.E., Linares-Roake, J. & Breen, A.V. What does One Health want? Feminist, posthuman, and anti-colonial possibilities. *One Health Outlook* 5, 4 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42522-022-00076-9>

6. Key Recommendations

Horefti, E. (2023). The Importance of the One Health Concept in Combating Zoonoses. In *Pathogens* (Vol. 12, Issue 8, p. 977). MDPI AG. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pathogens12080977>

Rodriguez Castañeda, N., Pineda-Pinto, M., Gulsrud, N. M., Cooper, C., O'Donnell, M., & Collier, M. (2024). Exploring the restorative capacity of urban green spaces and their biodiversity through an adapted One Health approach: A scoping review. In *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening* (Vol. 100, p. 128489). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2024.128489>

A.1: Mapping Resident Perspectives: PPGIS

Maptionnaire (2024). About Maptionnaire. <https://www.maptionnaire.com/>

A.3: Layering our data

Wang, T. (2016). Why Big Data Needs Thick Data. Medium: Ethnography Matters. <https://medium.com/ethnography-matters/why-big-data-needs-thick-data-b4b3e75e3d7>

